

Plant Favouritism: A Critical Discourse Analysis

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This study focuses on a variant of plant awareness disparity (PAD, formerly plant blindness), labelled as plant favouritism among Pre-Service Teachers (PSTs). The investigation is structured around three pivotal questions: (1) the influence of plant morphological traits on PSTs' choices, (2) the role of plant utility in shaping these preferences, and (3) the insights provided by CDA into the underlying factors that drive these selections. A key finding of the study is the identification of a significant taxonomic bias. This bias is evident as PSTs predominantly choose flowering or fruit-bearing plants, primarily influenced by their aesthetic qualities or direct benefits to humans. Non-flowering plants, despite their critical ecological roles, are considerably underrepresented in their selections. This taxonomic bias indicates a preference for certain types of plants based on their classification and visible traits. Additionally, the study uncovers a utilitarian bias in plant selection. This bias refers to the tendency of PSTs to favour plants that have practical uses or benefits for humans, such as those providing food, medicinal properties, or ornamental value. Such a bias suggests that the functional aspects of plants heavily influence PSTs' preferences, potentially at the expense of acknowledging the value of less utilitarian but ecologically significant species. The research highlights that these preferences are not solely based on personal likes and dislikes but are also deeply rooted in broader cultural, educational, and societal contexts. The study underscores the need to integrate Equity/Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) principles into botany education to promote a more balanced and comprehensive understanding of plant diversity.

Keywords: Plant Blindness, Teacher Education, Botany Education, Critical Discourse Analysis, EDI

Introduction

Background

Biodiversity, at its core, is an embodiment of variety and balance in the natural world. However, this balance is often disrupted by a lack of equity and inclusion in how we perceive and prioritize different life forms. This disparity is particularly evident in educational contexts, where plants frequently receive

less attention compared to animals. This skewed representation, highlighted by Brownlee et al. (2023) in their analysis of biology textbooks, not only mirrors but also reinforces systemic biases, impacting students' perceptions and valuations of ecological diversity. In addressing biodiversity, it is imperative to recognize and rectify these biases. The underrepresentation of plant species in educational materials not only reflects a narrow view of biodiversity but also raises questions about the values imparted to learners. As Adamo et al. (2022) have shown, the systemic neglect of plant species extends to the realm of conservation funding, with animals receiving significantly more support. This funding disparity, occurring over a period from 1992 to 2020, underscores a critical gap in our conservation efforts, one that could have long-term impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem health. The neglect of plant diversity in education and funding not only undermines the comprehensive understanding of ecosystems but also hampers the development of effective conservation strategies. Among the plant scientist community, the issue of equity manifests differently. The term "Plant Favouritism," as mentioned by Dixon (2021) and Burke et al. (2022), describes a bias towards plants that are aesthetically pleasing. This bias tends to favour plants with appealing visual characteristics, which can significantly influence scientific research and conservation priorities. Such preferential treatment might result in the inadvertent neglect of species that are less visually attractive but hold critical ecological importance. As highlighted by Adamo et al. (2021), this trend of overlooking less conspicuous plants can lead to imbalances in scientific understanding and conservation efforts, potentially disregarding the vital roles played by these less prominent species in ecosystems.

Plant favouritism rooted in "*Plant Blindness*," a concept introduced by Wandersee & Schussler (1999), describes the tendency to overlook plants, leading to their undervaluation. This term, however, has received criticism for its ableist connotations, as it metaphorically equates 'blindness' with a lack of awareness. The term "*Plant Awareness Disparity (PAD)*" (Parsley, 2020) has been proposed to address this issue more inclusively. PAD shifts the focus to the disparity in attention and appreciation plants receive compared to other life forms, avoiding negative implications associated with disabilities. Recent studies, like those by Marcos-Walias et al. (2023), reveal that PAD is not confined to textbooks but is prevalent at all levels of education. Kletečki et al. (2023) found that teachers value plants but see botany as a moderate educational priority, with biology teachers favouring more engaging methods to boost its appeal. Bobo-Pinilla et al. (2023) specifically reveal its strong presence among pre-service teachers and advocate integrating plant education topics into teacher training programs to address this. Parsley et al. (2022) and Pany et al. (2022) concentrate on developing assessment instruments, which are crucial for identifying the specific areas where educational interventions are needed to address PAD effectively. It is crucial to engage with all forms of plant life to foster a more inclusive understanding of biodiversity

and emotional connections to plants, as explored by Nyberg et al. (2019), and the integration of plants into sustainability discourse, as Thomas et al. (2021) suggest, are important for shaping inclusive and equitable attitudes towards all species. Creative approaches in education and media, as proposed by Balding & Williams (2016) and Kacprzyk et al. (2023), are essential in cultivating a more balanced and inclusive view of biodiversity.

The focus of the study

Based on the above background, this study focuses on examining how plant characteristics influence the selection preferences of pre-service science teachers (PSTs). By employing Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) (Fairclough, 2010), this study aims to explore how the form and function of plants affect the choices made by PSTs. In this context, “form” refers to the unique morphological traits of a plant, encompassing its structural as well as aesthetic features. At the same time, “function” pertains to the plant’s practical utility in human life and ecosystems. The term “selection preferences” here is defined as the criteria and considerations employed by PSTs when choosing plants in an educational setting. Such choices can significantly influence how biodiversity is represented and valued in educational settings, thus impacting the broader goals of equity and inclusion in science education. Specifically, this study addresses three pivotal research questions (RQs):

- **RQ1:** How do the unique morphological traits (form) of a plant influence the selection preferences of PSTs?
- **RQ2:** How does the practical utility (function) of a plant affect the selection preferences of PSTs?
- **RQ3:** How can Critical Discourse Analysis provide insights into the underlying factors driving the selection preferences among PSTs?

Through these questions, the study aims to shed light on the interplay between plant characteristics and educator preferences, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of how plant selection in science education can be aligned with the principles of equality/equity, diversity and inclusion.

Methodology

Data Collection

Participants were students enrolled on a science teacher training program in East Java, Indonesia, comprising 85 females and 15 males. Set within the context of a botany class lecture rich in local biodiversity, the study aimed to investigate plant favouritism in pre-service teacher education. The focus was on three key aspects: the specific plants of interest (type), their distinct visual and structural

aspects (form), and the plant's ecological role or utility in human life (function). The PSTs received a 10-minute briefing to establish their understanding of the topic. This briefing was then followed by a 10-minute preparation period, during which the PSTs organised their thoughts on the selected plants. Subsequently, each PST was given one minute to present their chosen plant. These presentations, emphasising the plant's type, form, and function, were video-recorded, averaging 59.47 seconds each ($SD \pm 12.99$ seconds), and then meticulously transcribed in the original language (*Bahasa Indonesia*) for detailed analysis.

Data Analysis

The study employed a dual approach: content analysis (Mayring, 2014) and Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) (Fairclough, 2010) to analyse those presentations. Through the content analysis of these transcripts, we meticulously looked for patterns and themes in how the PSTs described the type, form, and function of the plants. This process allowed us to uncover potential biases in plant representation and appreciation within the context of science education. Two experts in biology education conducted the content analysis. They assigned codes related to the type, form, and function of the plants to determine the PSTs' selection preferences. The reliability of this coding process was high, as indicated by a kappa coefficient (κ) of 0.96. CDA was crucial for delving deeper into the nuances of the PSTs' presentations. Representative excerpts (see Table 1) were selected for the CDA to explore how the broader context influenced the PSTs' selection preferences. CDA enabled a layered examination of the transcribed data, starting from the actual language used (*textual analysis*) to the way messages were crafted and communicated (*discursive practice*). The textual analysis included a focus on aspects such as tone, pacing, and emphasis. Furthermore, the analysis extended to understanding the broader sociocultural influences (*sociocultural practice*) shaping the PSTs' choices. Analysis of the second layer encompassed exploring how cultural norms, educational backgrounds, and the unique biodiversity of Indonesia might have influenced their selections. Through this comprehensive approach, the study aimed to not only highlight specific plant favouritism but also to unravel the broader cultural and educational implications of these preferential biases.

Table 1. Example of selected excerpts for the CDA

Excerpt	Type	Form	Function
<i>“I have always been a huge fan of chilli peppers, enjoying the heat and flavour they add to my meals. Recently, however, I’ve noticed that they have been getting increasingly expensive at the store, making me worried that it may become harder to afford in the future. To address this, I recently decided to grow my chilli peppers”</i> (Honey)	Solanales (Asterid)	Fruit	Plants as food and spice
<i>“One of the things that I love about the rose is its aesthetic versatility. It can be used in a variety of settings, from formal events like weddings to more casual settings like a backyard picnic. Whether they are cut and arranged in a vase or grown in a garden, roses always add a touch of elegance to any space.”</i> (Cathy)	Rosales (Dicots)	Flower	Plant as decoration

Note: names are pseudonyms, translation is approximate

Results

Conceptual Analysis Indicates Taxonomic, Aesthetic and Utility Biases

In our content analysis, we discovered a significant trend we termed “*Taxonomic Bias*,” highlighted by the overwhelming preference for flowering or fruiting plants among the 24 unique plant groups analysed by participants. An astounding 99% of PSTs focused their presentations on these plants, particularly favouring taxonomic groups such as Rosales (e.g., Roses), Lamiales (e.g., Mints), Caryophyllales (e.g., Carnations), and Asterales (e.g., Sunflowers). Interest in flowering plants contrasted sharply with the attention given to non-flowering plants, where only a single mention of a moss plant was noted, representing a mere 1% of the total. Data from our study, illustrated in Figures 1 to 3, paints a detailed picture of this bias. Figure 1 shows the taxonomic distribution of selected plants, highlighting a strong inclination towards certain groups. Figure 2 details functional preferences, with flowers (30%) and fruits (33%) being the most popular choices, followed by leaves (21%) and other parts like roots, stems, and bulbs (16%). Further analysis of Figure 3 highlights a trend termed “*Utilitarian Bias*,” where the mentioned function of these plants is evident. A substantial 52% are utilized for food and spices, 32% for ornamental purposes, 12% for medicinal uses, 3% serve as timber, and a mere 1% are recognized for their ecological roles, such as nutrient cycling. This distribution underscores a clear bias in selection. These favouring plants are aesthetically appealing or have direct utilitarian value to humans. Beyond taxonomic classifications, the analysis also uncovered biases linked to the aesthetic qualities and practical utilities of the chosen plants. PSTs’ selections were evidently influenced not just by the botanical identity of the plants but also by their visual appeal and the

benefits they offer to human life, especially in the preference for flowering and fruiting plants, often selected for their tangible contributions to everyday life, including food provision and ornamental value.

Critical Discourse Analysis Implies the Underlying Factors of the Biases

In applying Fairclough's first dimension of textual analysis, as illustrated in Table 2, we discerned a distinct pattern in the descriptive language used by participants. When discussing plants with prominent flowers, such as Roses and Tulips, participants employed emotive vocabulary. Terms like "beautiful" and "elegant" were frequently used, indicating an emotional or aesthetic connection. This language choice, involving expressive adjectives, as noted in the 'Vocabulary and Phrasing' section of Table 2, reflects a deep-seated appreciation for these plants' visual attributes. Additionally, the use of active verbs, such as in the phrase "Roses captivate," positions these plants as dynamic entities in human experiences. This active engagement with the subject is further highlighted by the use of rich metaphors, exemplified by phrases like "Roses are the crown jewels of the garden," which amplify their perceived value and appeal. Conversely, plants with less conspicuous flowers, such as Lettuce and Moss, were characterised using more utilitarian or neutral descriptors like "nutritious," "edible," or "common." This linguistic treatment, leaning towards passive, neutral, or factual verbs as outlined in the 'Grammar and Syntax' section of Table 2, fosters a more detached, observational perspective. These plants were seldom the subjects of expressive techniques. When rhetorical devices were employed, they were usually minimal or practical, such as stating, "Lettuce is part of a healthy diet."

Moving to Fairclough's second dimension, discursive practices, as presented in Table 3, we observed trends in speech construction and presentation nuances. Even under the constrained setting of a 10-minute preparation period without external resources, participant choices favoured familiar or visually appealing plants, which is exemplified in expressions like "I chose the rose because it's not only beautiful but also universally recognised." Such choices, aligning with entrenched societal values, were accompanied by enhanced enthusiasm and more dynamic peer engagement when discussing visually appealing plants like sunflowers. This pattern suggests that societal biases favour certain types of plants, as reflected in the peer engagement findings where the audience's reactions—more eye contact, nods, and questions—were more pronounced for flowering plants. Lastly, Fairclough's third dimension, sociocultural practices, as detailed in Table 4, compels us to consider the broader context. These linguistic and discursive patterns are not isolated phenomena but are entwined with larger ideological and social contexts.

Figure 1. Types of plant categorised by taxonomic group (as per Angiosperm Phylogeny Group IV System): blue bars (■) refer to non-flowering plants, while orange bars (■) refer to flowering plants (angiosperms).

Figure 2. Tabulation of codes related with form.

Figure 3. Tabulation of codes related with function.

Table 2. Analysis of the textual elements.

Factor/ Plant Type	Plants with Obvious Flowers (e.g., Roses, Tulips)	Plants with Less Obvious Flowers (e.g., Lettuce) and Moss
Vocabulary and Phrasing	Expressive adjectives (e.g., “beautiful,” “elegant“)	Utilitarian or neutral descriptors (e.g., “nutritious,” “edible,” “green,” “common“)
Grammar and Syntax	Active verbs (e.g., “Roses captivate“)	Passive, neutral, or factual verbs (e.g., “Lettuce is eaten,” “Moss grows on rocks“)
Rhetorical Devices	Expressive techniques like metaphors (e.g. “Roses are the crown jewels of the garden“)	Minimal or practical rhetorical devices (e.g. “Lettuce is the part of a healthy diet“)

Table 3. Analysis of the discursive practice.

Factor	Finding	Excerpt
Speech Construction	Choices favour familiar or visually appealing plants	<i>“I chose the rose because it’s not only beautiful but also universally recognised.”</i>
Presentation Nuances	Enhanced enthusiasm and	<i>“The sunflower is just so vibrant and full of life!”</i> (noted enthusiastic tone and gestures)
Peer Engagement	Increased attention and feedback for flowering plants	Audience reactions: more eye contact, nods, and questions like, <i>“Where can I grow it?”</i>

Table 4. Analysis of the sociocultural practices.

Factor	Finding	Example
Ideological Underpinning	Non-native plants are commodified and ingrained as points of interest due to the colonial past.	PSTs picked coffee, touted for its economic value but not its non-native status in Indonesia.
Social Context: Gender Constructs	Choices align with societal gender roles.	Females focus on “beauty” (e.g. Rose), males on “utility.” (e.g. teak)
Educational Implications	Choices may forecast future teaching biases.	Preference for flowering plants, hinting at limited teaching scope

For instance, the preference for non-native plants hints at the legacy of colonialism in Indonesia. Coffee was introduced and extensively cultivated for its high economic value; a practice deeply rooted in the colonial agenda of resource exploitation. The history of coffee has left a lasting imprint; the plant, now ingrained in the local culture and economy, continues to be celebrated for its commercial importance. Additionally, the alignment of choices with traditional gender roles – with females often choosing aesthetically pleasing plants like roses and males opting for utilitarian plants like teak – indicates how societal constructs and norms influence these preferences. The plant favouritism extends to educational implications, suggesting that such biases may forecast future teaching biases, potentially limiting the scope of plant-related teaching to predominantly flowering species.

Discussion

Addressing RQ1: Influence of Plant Form on Selection Preferences

In regards to the first RQ, our findings reveal a compelling trend: PSTs predominantly favour plants with distinct and visually appealing morphological features, particularly those with vibrant flowers or fruits. This preference underscores a deep-seated aesthetic bias in plant selection, reflecting a broader human inclination towards visually attractive objects. Studies such as those by Hůla and Flegr (2016, 2020) show that this attraction is not solely based on evolutionary signals of food availability but also aesthetic preferences for

certain flower colours and shapes. The allure of flowering plants like roses and tulips can be partly attributed to their vivid colours, intricate structures, and the general perception of flowers as symbols of beauty and vitality. Ruiz-Hernández et al. (2021) further suggest that human preferences for certain flower types might align with those of pollinators, adding an evolutionary perspective to our aesthetic choices. This aesthetic appeal of flowers is deeply rooted in cultural and historical contexts. Across various cultures, flowers have held significant symbolic meanings, often associated with positive emotions, celebrations, and important life events.

Consequently, PSTs' preference for flowering plants could be seen as a reflection of these ingrained cultural values. However, this bias towards aesthetically pleasing plants raises critical pedagogical concerns. By favouring flowering plants, there is a risk of marginalising other plant groups that are less visually striking but ecologically essential. Non-flowering plants like ferns, mosses, and gymnosperms, though lacking the immediate visual appeal of flowering plants, play indispensable roles in ecosystems. Studies addressing plant blindness, like those by Kissi and Dreesmann (2022) and Thomas et al. (2022), highlight the importance of incorporating diverse plant forms in education. These studies emphasise that innovative approaches, such as mobile learning and the Pet Plant Project by Krosnick et al. (2018), can enhance student engagement with a variety of plants, including non-flowering ones. Suppose these plants are underrepresented in educational settings due to their less appealing morphology. In that case, students may receive a skewed understanding of botanical diversity and the importance of different plant forms in ecosystems.

Furthermore, this aesthetic bias could inadvertently lead to a superficial approach to botanical education, where the focus is placed more on the external beauty of plants rather than their ecological functions, evolutionary history, or biological mechanisms. Therefore, educators need to recognise and address this aesthetic bias in plant selection. Educators need to consciously include a diverse range of plant forms in their teaching, ensuring that the more aesthetically appealing ones do not overshadow the less visually striking plants. By doing so, they can provide a more equitable and inclusive representation of plant life, fostering a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of botanical diversity among future generations.

Addressing RQ2: Impact of Plant Utility on Selection Preferences

The second RQ delves into how the practical utility or function of plants shapes the selection preferences of PSTs. Our study's findings are particularly revealing, indicating a pronounced "utilitarian bias" in plant selection. This bias underscores the emphasis on plants' functional roles, especially those with direct human benefits, such as food, medicine, and ornamentation, as noted

by Reinaldo et al. (2020), who found that taxonomic affiliation influences the selection of medicinal plants, reflecting the practical utility that resonates with PSTs. For instance, apple trees and medicinal herbs are popular choices due to their clear and direct applications in everyday human life. These plants provide tangible examples to illustrate concepts like pollination, photosynthesis, and medicinal properties in ways that connect with students' experiences. However, this utilitarian bias can inadvertently narrow the scope of botanical education. Plants that lack obvious direct utility for humans, such as certain grasses or non-flowering plants, may be undervalued or overlooked. This oversight, a manifestation of 'PAD' as discussed by Balding & Williams (2016), fails to acknowledge the true diversity and ecological significance of all plants. Grasses, for example, are essential for soil stabilisation and are a primary food source for various wildlife species. Yet, their significance is often overshadowed due to their less apparent benefits to humans. Similarly, non-flowering plants like mosses in the ecosystems contribute significantly to carbon sequestration in soil, among other roles. The preference for plants with evident human utility reflects a broader societal trend of assessing the value of natural resources primarily through their utility to humans. This perspective can lead to a skewed understanding of the environment and its components. To counteract this bias, it's critical to broaden the scope of botanical education, as suggested by Colon et al. (2020), who demonstrated that immersive botanical experiences can positively shift perceptions of botany and reduce PAD. Educators should aim to highlight the importance of all plant species, regardless of their direct utility to humans, as underscored by Jose et al. (2019) in their advocacy for a central role of plants in biological education. This more holistic approach to plant education would not only foster a deeper appreciation for plant diversity but also instil a sense of responsibility towards conserving all forms of plant life. By expanding educational focus beyond mere utilitarian aspects, PSTs can develop a more balanced understanding of the environment, recognising the intrinsic value of all plants in sustaining ecological health and biodiversity.

Addressing RQ3: Insights from Critical Discourse Analysis on Plant Selection Preferences

Addressing the third research question, CDA offers invaluable insights into the deeper, often subconscious factors influencing PSTs' selection preferences for certain plants. This analytical approach reveals how the language and discourse used by PSTs are not merely individual choices but are embedded within broader societal, cultural, and educational contexts. The language used by PSTs in describing plants, particularly flowering species, often carries connotations that go beyond botanical characteristics, as noted by Sartillot (1993) in "*Herbarium Verbarium: The Discourse of Flowers*," which explores the symbolic significance of flowers in literature and society. For instance, flowering plants are frequently

described in emotive, vibrant language that imbues them with qualities such as beauty, elegance, and charm. This kind of discourse not only reflects a societal appreciation for aesthetic values but also indicates an underlying anthropocentric view where plants are often valued for their appeal or usefulness to humans. In contrast, non-flowering plants, which may lack immediate visual appeal or obvious practical value, are often described in more neutral or functional terms. This linguistic distinction subtly reinforces the perception that flowering plants are more significant or valuable. Furthermore, CDA helps to unravel how cultural narratives shape PSTs' perceptions of plants. For instance, the prominence of certain plants in textbooks, media, and cultural symbolism can predispose PSTs to favour these plants. This preference is not just a matter of personal taste. Still, it is influenced by a complex interplay of educational exposure, cultural norms, and even historical factors such as colonialism. Baber (2016), in "*The Plants of Empire: Botanic Gardens, Colonial Power and Botanical Knowledge*", highlights how botanical gardens played a role in the colonial transfer of plants, thereby shaping perceptions of plant value based on their economic utility, such as the preference for non-native plants like coffee. The insights gained from CDA have profound implications for botanical education. They suggest that to counteract the biases and misconceptions leading to a narrowed focus on certain plant types, there is a need for a more critical and reflective approach in science education. Educators should be encouraged to not only teach about a wide variety of plants but also to critically examine and discuss the reasons behind the prevalent preferences for certain types. This approach would help PSTs to recognise and question their biases, fostering a more inclusive understanding of plant diversity. Moreover, it can lead to a more balanced curriculum that equally values all plant species, thereby promoting a more comprehensive view of biodiversity. Overall, Critical Discourse Analysis serves as a powerful tool for understanding and addressing the factors underlying plant selection preferences among PSTs. By incorporating these insights into educational strategies, it is possible to develop a more nuanced, equitable, and inclusive approach to botanical education, one that truly reflects the diversity and significance of all plant life.

Implication of the Findings: Integrating EDI Principles in Botanical Education

The study's findings and subsequent analysis have profound implications for botanical education, emphasising the need for a more inclusive and balanced approach that integrates Equality/Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) principles. This approach is crucial to address the prevalent biases in botanical education, especially those favouring plants with aesthetic appeal or direct human utility. These biases can significantly limit students' understanding of the vast diversity and ecological significance of plant life, including less visually striking but ecologically important species like ferns, mosses, and gymnosperms. The

study conducted by Brownlee et al. (2023) and others illuminate the systemic biases impacting how students perceive and value ecological diversity. The underrepresentation of certain plant species in educational materials highlights the need for both ecological and educational equity. Adamo et al. (2022) and subsequent studies further reveal the systemic neglect of plant species in conservation funding, underscoring potential long-term impacts on biodiversity and ecosystem health. This bias extends to scientific research, as shown by Adamo et al. (2021), where the focus tends to be on aesthetically appealing plants. To counter these biases, educators must consciously include a broader range of plants in their curriculum, fostering a deeper appreciation for all forms of plant life and their roles in ecosystems. This means not only enriching students' knowledge but also encouraging critical thinking and reflection on the reasons behind plant selection preferences, including cultural, historical, and societal influences. The study's responses to Research Questions (RQs) shed further light on these biases. In response to RQ1, the study reveals an aesthetic bias in plant selection. At the same time, RQ2 highlights a utilitarian bias, emphasising plants with direct human benefits. Addressing RQ3 through Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) exposes the deeper societal, cultural, and educational factors influencing these preferences. Integrating EDI principles in botanical education involves a shift from a purely utilitarian perspective to a more holistic view, promoting a sense of responsibility and stewardship towards all forms of plant life. This could involve project-based learning, field trips to diverse ecosystems, interactions with botanical experts, and leveraging technology to showcase the beauty and importance of less popular plants. Ultimately, this requires a concerted effort from educators, curriculum developers, and the wider educational community.

Limitations and Recommendations

The study provides valuable insights into plant selection biases among prospective science teachers. Yet, it has certain limitations that pave the way for further research. Its focus on a specific geographic area, East Java, Indonesia, suggests the need for similar studies across various cultural and geographical contexts to gain a more global understanding of these biases. Methodologically, the reliance on CDA and presentations for data collection might not capture all nuanced biases. Future research could benefit from a mix of methods, such as surveys or interviews, to obtain a broader perspective. Furthermore, the study mainly considers the morphological and utilitarian aspects of plants. Expanding the scope to include ecological, evolutionary, or cultural factors could provide a more comprehensive view of what influences plant selection in education. Another area for further research is examining how these educator biases are perceived and internalised by students, offering insights for developing more effective educational strategies. Lastly, exploring how plant selection biases

manifest across different educational levels and settings and assessing the impact of interventions aimed at reducing these biases would be beneficial for enhancing botanical education. This could involve longitudinal studies to track changes over time and the effectiveness of different pedagogical approaches.

Conclusion

This research critically examines the plant favouritism of PSTs in East Java, Indonesia. Addressing the research questions: (RQ1) the influence of plant morphological traits on PSTs' selections, (RQ2) the impact of plant utility on these preferences, and (RQ3) insights from CDA on the underlying factors, the findings reveal a pronounced bias towards aesthetically appealing and utilitarian plants. This preference often leads to the neglect of ecologically crucial but less visually striking species, reflecting cultural and educational influences. The study emphasises the need to integrate EDI principles in botanical education to ensure a more balanced and comprehensive understanding of biodiversity. It highlights the importance of expanding educational content to represent a diverse range of plant life, addressing the biases revealed in RQ1 and RQ2. Furthermore, the insights from CDA (RQ3) suggest that these biases are deeply embedded in societal and cultural contexts, necessitating a more critical approach to teaching.

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